

MODERN MECHANISMS FOR THE PREVENTION OF JUVENILE DELINQUENCY

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific-theoretical and practical analysis of modern preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing crimes committed by minors. The study examines the causes of juvenile delinquency, the role of social environment, family, educational institutions, as well as state and non-state institutions in this process based on a comprehensive approach. Additionally, alongside traditional prevention methods, the importance of digital technologies, individual prevention, early warning systems, psychological and pedagogical assistance, and mechanisms of interdepartmental cooperation is highlighted. Based on the experience of foreign countries, effective mechanisms aimed at reducing juvenile delinquency are analyzed, and scientific conclusions and practical proposals for improving the application of national law are developed.

Keywords: minors, crime prevention, individual prevention, socially dangerous situation, early warning, preventive monitoring, psychological and pedagogical measures, interdepartmental cooperation, digital prevention, delinquency prevention.

Today, the sharp increase in modern risks and threats emerging in the social environment, including the presence of international terrorism and religious extremism (ideological influence and radicalization of youth), illegal migration and human trafficking (deprivation of minors of sufficient supervision and support, thereby increasing their propensity for crime), as well as the spread of ideas alien to our people among young people (dangerous ideological environment) are having a negative socio-ideological impact on the growth of juvenile delinquency. At the same time, crimes such as premeditated murder, intentional infliction of bodily harm, theft, robbery, fraud, hooliganism, rape, and extortion in everyday life, and their traditional nature of occurrence (social models of deviant behavior) serve as significant factors in increasing the propensity for delinquency among minors.

The aforementioned risks and threats require internal affairs bodies to establish new objectives in the field of juvenile delinquency prevention. These circumstances also increase the need to create modern preventive mechanisms and integrate them into practice, which necessitates changes in legislation, the development of psychological and pedagogical methodologies, and the implementation of social and technological measures. Furthermore, these measures will serve to increase the effectiveness of juvenile delinquency prevention through their application in a coordinated system.

The legislation defines internal affairs bodies as the main and priority subject in the fight against crime. In the activities of these bodies, interaction with all state bodies, educational institutions, social and preventive organizations responsible for working with children, bodies of citizen self-government, and civil society institutions is of particular importance. This cooperation is carried out on the basis of the principle of "unity of action" and provides for the introduction of specific practical mechanisms that ensure coordinated, systematic, and effective interaction between these entities. In practice, these mechanisms play an important role in ensuring multifaceted cooperation among minors, increasing the effectiveness of preventive and crime prevention measures.

The conducted scientific research determined the relevance of developing and improving modern organizational, legal, and practical mechanisms for the effective organization of crime prevention among minors. The scientific conclusions formed on this basis make it possible to develop specific recommendations and scientifically based proposals for strengthening the legal basis of activities for the prevention of juvenile delinquency, improving institutional cooperation between authorized state bodies and social institutions, and effectively organizing preventive measures in practice.

In the process of reforms being implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the priority directions of state policy are defined, in particular, within the framework of the "Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan" for 2022-2026, the tasks of protecting human rights, including the rights and interests of minors, ensuring their social security, early detection of offenses, and eliminating their consequences are of particular importance. At the same time, the growing trend of juvenile delinquency in society, the fact that these crimes often belong to socially vulnerable and vulnerable segments of the population, as well as the growing need for crime prevention among the population, make it even more urgent to comprehensively improve the sphere of crime prevention among minors.

Based on the goals and objectives of the dissertation research, as well as the results of the analysis, the following main conclusions were made in the field of crime prevention among minors:

a) in order to more effectively organize the prevention of crimes among minors, it is necessary to deeply analyze its theoretical foundations and revise them based on modern scientific approaches. This, in turn, strengthens the methodological and conceptual foundations of preventive activities.

b) one of the urgent tasks is the development and implementation of effective preventive mechanisms against juvenile delinquency, taking into account the prevalence and trends of crime. These mechanisms include legal, psychological-pedagogical, social, and technological components, and their mutual harmony ensures the effectiveness of prevention;

c) in order to increase the effectiveness of work in this area, it is necessary to strengthen the legal framework and eliminate gaps in current legislation and law enforcement practice. This implies strengthening institutional cooperation and legal guarantees in preventive activities.

d) it is important to develop and effectively implement innovative preventive mechanisms for the prevention of crimes among minors in accordance with modern requirements. These mechanisms are based on modern pedagogical, psychological, and social approaches, while also allowing for the creation of a clear monitoring and evaluation system in preventive activities.

Within the framework of the conducted research, the state of theoretical, organizational, legal, and methodological support for the prevention of crimes among minors, as well as current rules and their current state, were comprehensively analyzed. Based on the results of this analysis, priority areas for the harmonious improvement of mechanisms for the prevention of juvenile delinquency were identified, and the goal was set to develop them on a scientific basis.

Analysis of the practice of juvenile crime prevention and the experience of foreign countries in this area shows that modern mechanisms for the prevention of crimes in any field of prevention, including among minors, are, first of all, a harmonized system of comprehensive measures aimed at the early prevention of crimes committed by this category of persons, ensuring their social, legal, and psychological rehabilitation. Modern preventive mechanisms, unlike traditional punitive and educational methods, imply an integrated approach to the individual's individual and social environment[1].

These modern mechanisms consist of legislative, psychological-pedagogical, social, and technological components, the harmony of which serves as the main factor in increasing the effectiveness of preventive measures.

The structure of legislation defines the processes of preventing crimes among minors, protecting juvenile rights, and bringing them to legal responsibility.

The psychological and pedagogical component encompasses educational, upbringing, and psychological support in accordance with the individual characteristics and development level of the individual.

social structure implies the integration of youth into the social environment and their support through family, school, mahalla, and public institutions.

ensures the effective organization of the prevention process through electronic monitoring, online consultations, information and communication tools, and other innovative means.

Thus, when these structures work in cooperation and harmony, it is possible to achieve high efficiency in reducing juvenile delinquency and ensuring their socio-legal and psychological stability.

First direction: improvement of existing legal mechanisms in legislation.

The first and priority direction in increasing the effectiveness of juvenile delinquency prevention is the improvement of existing legal mechanisms in legislation. Currently, the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan provides for separate norms on juvenile delinquency, including mechanisms for organizing juvenile justice and applying preventive measures established by law, but in practice, their effectiveness and integrated application are limited in some cases.

The main directions for improving the existing legal mechanisms of legislation should include:

1) Modernization of legislation on juvenile delinquency, that is, in this process, it is necessary to review existing norms based on modern social and psychological-pedagogical analysis, expand preventive measures in laws, and strengthen an integrated approach. It is also important to clearly define and coordinate the powers in the activities of the courts, prosecutor's office, internal affairs bodies, and social services[2].

2) Development of juvenile courts and alternative sanctions mechanisms, that is, the application of restorative and diversion mechanisms in the process of considering offenses committed by minors in court, as well as strengthening the legal basis for various compulsory and educational measures[3].

3) Legal justification of institutional cooperation, that is, the clear definition in legislation of cooperation with all authorized bodies, educational institutions, local public and civil society institutions in the prevention of minors, ensuring systematic activity between them based on the principle of harmony and "unity of action"[4].

4) In the process of improving legislation, based on international experience, in particular, the experience of the USA, Korea, Japan, and China, the issue of providing preventive measures, legal education, and rehabilitation mechanisms in the prevention of juvenile delinquency on the basis of legislation is of particular relevance[5].

In general, the improvement of existing legal mechanisms in legislation is one of the priority areas in bringing the prevention of juvenile delinquency into line with modern requirements and increasing the effectiveness of preventive measures.

First direction:

1) The tasks defined in Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" of September 29, 2010, cover the main, basic directions of activities for the prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors, i.e., determine the main goal, objectives, and general direction of the subjects responsible for the prevention system. These tasks are theoretically correct and sufficient, but based on modern preventive requirements, international experience, innovative safety mechanisms, and the principles of juvenile justice, these tasks need to be classified, expanded, and clarified.

The insufficiency of the tasks defined in Article 4 of the Law is manifested in the following aspects:

In international practice (UN, UNICEF, Council of Europe), three levels of prevention are defined - universal, selective, indicated prevention (general, selective, and indicative prevention), these areas are not reflected in the law;

preventive activities should cover not only the regulation of behavior, but also the socialization of the child, education, psychological support, digital security, protection from online delinquency (there are no such areas in practice);

modern mechanisms such as institutional cooperation between subjects, digital prevention technologies, risk assessment, and a restorative justice system do not have the status of legislative tasks;

the statute of juvenile justice (separate courts, mediation, probation, diversion) is not clearly defined in the content of the tasks of the law.

Based on the foregoing, it is recommended to supplement Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 29, 2010 "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" with the following additional clauses:

- "coordination of the activities of entities carrying out and participating in the prevention of offenses, neglect, and homelessness among minors";

- "assessment of social, psychological, educational, and family risk factors that determine the likelihood of juvenile delinquency";

- "ensuring the digital security of minors, forming their media literacy and information culture."

2) When analyzing the text of Article 7 of the Law from a legal point of view, no clear legal collision (contradiction between legal norms) is observed, but there are controversial cases where repetition, misunderstanding, and interpretation in practice can cause problems. These circumstances, from the point of view of legal technique, are not a normative-legal conflict, but a legal-technical problem.

Firstly, the existing problems are manifested in the duplication of the same norm.

The first part of the article sets the task of not allowing them to be in places such as restaurants, cafes, clubs, cinemas, and internet halls. In the second part, a repetition of the same norm is given, only with the addition "at night."

This sometimes leads to misunderstandings: a) the first clause establishes a prohibition that is not tied to time at all; b) the second clause sets the task of preventing being without parental supervision only at night.

The question arises: if parents are present at night, is it permissible for minors to be in these places? If an analytical answer is given to this question; a) according to the first part of the norm, it is not allowed at all; b) according to the second part, if a parent or one of them is present at night, it may be allowed.

Secondly, the concept of "other entertainment venues" is an ambiguous legal term that creates controversial situations in theory and practice.

The article uses the concept of "other entertainment (leisure) places," which in the legal doctrine is considered an "uncertain legal category."

It has become unclear whether this concept includes: a) park; b) shopping centers; c) karaoke; d) billiard hall; e) bowling center.

Thirdly, the concept of "Nighttime" is not clearly defined.

The article uses the legal term "night time," but does not specify its exact time limit (for example: 22:00-06:00).

If this concept is not defined in other laws, then a legal gap (gap in law) arises in the article.

Based on the above analysis, it should be noted that although the text of Article 7 does not directly cause a legal conflict, it notes that it does not fully comply with the requirements of

legal technique, some norms are duplicated, there are ambiguous legal concepts, and it can cause problems in interpretation in practice.

Based on the foregoing, it is recommended to supplement Article 7 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 29, 2010 "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" with the following additional clauses:

"Article 7. Participation of parents or guardians in the prevention of neglect and delinquency among minors.

Parents or persons replacing parents are obliged to take the necessary measures to protect the physical, spiritual, and intellectual development, life, and health of the child, to prevent his neglect and delinquency, as well as to prevent socially dangerous situations.

Parents or persons replacing parents are obliged to prevent the presence of minors in the following circumstances:

in restaurants, cafes, bars, discos, cinemas, computer halls, internet cafes, and other entertainment (leisure) venues, except in cases of participation in educational, cultural, educational, or legally established events;

be present in these places at night (from 22:00 to 06:00) in the absence of parents or persons replacing them;

Consumption or smoking of alcoholic beverages, narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, electronic tobacco products, nicotine consumption products and other substances affecting intellectual and volitional activity;

creation of conditions for the commission of offenses or other antisocial acts.

The "entertainment (leisure) places" specified in the second part of this article are understood to be a special place, service facility or electronic environment intended for cultural, interactive, dining, computer, virtual, sports, entertainment, gambling or other types of recreational activities of persons.

Failure of parents or persons replacing parents to fulfill the obligations established by this article entails administrative or criminal liability in accordance with the legislation."

3) It is proposed to supplement the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Offenses among Minors" of September 29, 2010, with Articles 241 and 242.

"Article 24-1. The concept of social prevention among minors.

Social prevention among minors is a set of systematic, targeted, and comprehensive socio-organizational measures implemented by society, families, educational institutions, mahallas, and state bodies, aimed at preventing minors from falling into situations of delinquency, neglect, and abandonment.

"Article 24-2. Social prevention measures among minors.

formation of a healthy psychological atmosphere in the family, increasing responsibility for the upbringing of the child, providing social assistance to troubled families;

identification and social rehabilitation of families in a problematic and socially dangerous situation;

strengthening educational work in general education, secondary specialized, and higher educational institutions, organizing preventive conversations, legal literacy classes, and socio-ethical trainings;

organization of a healthy lifestyle, meaningful organization of leisure time, sports and cultural events for minors with the participation of the mahalla "seven," the Agency for Youth Affairs, NGOs and other public structures;

provision of psychological, legal, medical, pedagogical, and material assistance to minors and their families;

Assistance to problematic children and families through the "Youth Notebook," "Women's Notebook," and "Iron Notebook" platforms;

Development of individual rehabilitation programs with the participation of psychologists, sociologists, educators and law enforcement officers;

Formation of legal culture among young people through the mass media, social networks, and a positive attitude and active participation in prevention among the general public.

In general, the adoption of this norm will serve not only to prevent the commission of offenses by certain individuals through social preventive measures, but also to activate a systematic preventive mechanism aimed at improving the social environment, ensuring the healthy social adaptation of young people, and forming a responsible civic position in them.

Second direction: education, upbringing, and socio-psychological assistance in accordance with the individual characteristics and level of development of the minor.

One of the main directions of prevention is the effective implementation of education and upbringing in accordance with the individual characteristics and level of development of the minor. This direction is based on the need to determine targeted pedagogical and psychological measures of influence, taking into account the age, intellectual potential, psychological state, level of adaptation to the social environment, and individual needs of the minor. Scientific research shows that unified standard measures do not give the same result for each child, while preventive measures organized on the basis of an individual approach allow achieving stable positive results.

Educational institutions, together with psychologists, teachers, social workers, and prevention inspectors, must develop development maps for minors. These cards define the individual's psychotype, abilities, interests, behavioral deviations, and individual rehabilitation plans aimed at their correction. At the same time, based on correctional pedagogy, psychological rehabilitation, stress resistance training, training aimed at developing emotional intelligence and the skills of making correct decisions in problem situations are conducted.

The experience of foreign countries confirms the effectiveness of this direction. In Germany, the "Jugendgerichtsgesetz" law allows for correction and re-education based on an individual approach for young people, and also prioritizes psychodiagnostics, socio-psychological counseling, family mediation, and social adaptation measures. In Great Britain, the "Whole System Approach" (WSA) concept relies on cooperation between state, educational, family, and community institutions. Based on this concept, "Youth Offending Teams" were created, which act as a link between the school, mahalla, and police systems. In France, the "Protection Judiciaire de la Jeunesse" system implements preventive measures through extrajudicial diversion, family mediation, psychological therapy, and programs aimed at social activity. In the Netherlands, the "Prevention Through Responsibility" (Preventie met Gezag) and "Halt" programs are aimed at providing educational tasks for young people instead of punishment, reducing risks in schools and mahallas, and ensuring social reintegration. In the Swedish welfare model, social services are organized effectively and conveniently for clients, and preventive measures are carried out in cooperation with social workers, psychologists, and local authorities.

On this basis, proposals can be formulated as follows:

Implementation of psychodiagnostics and development maps of minors in schools and mahallas for the introduction of an individual approach to juvenile prevention in Uzbekistan;
development of a system that ensures integrated interaction between teachers, psychologists, and social workers;

expansion of family mediation and psychological counseling services, as well as ensuring close interaction with the family and the mahalla;

development of individual prevention programs for young people based on the best practices of foreign countries, using the models of Germany, Great Britain, the Netherlands, and Sweden;

widespread use of modern technologies in prevention, namely electronic monitoring, online psychological and legal consultations.

Third direction: integration and support of youth in the social environment through family, school, mahalla, and public institutions

The full adaptation of a minor to the social environment determines the effectiveness of their socialization process. From a scientific point of view, socialization is the process of stable, positive, and natural integration of the individual into the system of rules, values, social roles, and relationships accepted in society. In this process, the family, school, mahalla, NGOs, youth organizations, and other public institutions play an important role as primary and secondary agents of socialization.

The family is the primary school of upbringing for a child. In it, the foundations of moral values, customs, respect, responsibility, empathy, and social discipline are formed. And the school, through the educational and pedagogical organizational environment, ensures the intellectual development, legal literacy, and social activity of the individual. Through the mahalla, the Youth Union, NGOs, and volunteer organizations, young people are involved in community life and are encouraged to actively participate in social events. Thus, public institutions form a mutually integrated preventive platform, strengthening the socialization of the minor.

The Canadian experience is also significant as one of the advanced models in this area. There, special clubs will be organized for children aged 6-11 in the risk group to prevent juvenile delinquency. Clubs have a preventive effect by developing children's social activity and ensuring a safe environment in the after-school period (15:00-18:00). The Youth Criminal Justice Act (YCJA) also includes alternative sanctions, diversion, probation, and social support mechanisms for young people. In the Canadian experience, restorative practices, such as "healing circles" and mediation, are prioritized for reintegration into society and the formation of a sense of responsibility.

Based on this, the following proposals can be developed in this area:

Creation of centers and clubs for social activities after school in Uzbekistan, ensuring the employment of children and protecting them from a hazardous environment;

Establishing an integrated prevention system for young people by strengthening cooperation between the family, school, and the mahalla institute;

introduction of restorative practices and mediation for young people, thereby forming their reintegration into society and a sense of responsibility;

application of educational measures instead of punishment for young people who have committed an offense for the first time by expanding alternative sanctions, diversion, and probation programs;

development of social support measures with the participation of the public, NGOs and volunteer institutions, and creation of an appropriate preventive environment for problem groups.

Fourth direction: effective organization of the prevention process through electronic monitoring, online consultations, information and communication tools, and other innovative technologies

It is impossible to fully imagine a modern prevention system without digital technologies. According to socio-psychological analysis, the consciousness of modern youth is highly dependent on the digital media environment in receiving, analyzing, and responding to information. Therefore, organizing preventive processes through remote platforms, electronic profiles, online monitoring, and remote consultations significantly increases efficiency.

With the help of an electronic preventive account (e-prevention), information about the social status, psychological dynamics, attitude to education, activities, and needs of a minor is collected in a single preventive database. Through this database, it is possible to ensure an individual approach to the individual, monitor and predict their behavior.

Online psychological counseling platforms are important in providing anonymous psychological support, legal assistance, and social counseling to young people. Through information and communication systems, young people acquire media culture, internet

security, and cyber-legal literacy, which ensures their safe navigation in the information environment.

Also, chatbots, resilience index, risk level monitoring, virtual trainings, rehabilitation simulators, and online diagnostic tools are being widely implemented in the prevention process. Thanks to this, preventive activities will have an individual, dynamic, and predictive character, that is, measures adapted to the situation and needs of each minor will be applied.

Suggestions:

Monitoring the social and psychological state of minors, monitoring their participation in preventive measures, and determining individual measures based on data.

provision of anonymous and accessible counseling services for young people, reduction of stress and deviant behavior.

creation of integrated modules for achieving media culture, internet security, and cyber-legal literacy.

individualization and improvement of the effectiveness of preventive activities through chatbots, virtual trainings, rehabilitation simulators, and the courage index.

Establishment of a mechanism for assessing the effectiveness of preventive measures for minors based on the results of electronic monitoring and their prompt modification.

Fifth direction: Legal education of minors.

Legal education of minors is a systematic, continuous, and purposeful educational and pedagogical activity aimed at forming their legal consciousness, legal culture, legal responsibility, and legal behavior. This direction is the most important system-forming link in prevention, because a person with legal knowledge understands the essence of rights, understands obligations, and can predict the consequences of unlawful actions.

From a scientific point of view, the main tasks of legal education include:

formation in minors of concepts of law, law, and legal relations;

fostering respect for legal values, the principle of legality, the concepts of equality and justice;

formation of the ability to comply with legal norms, a negative attitude towards the offense;

development of a critical attitude to external influences leading to offenses, the ability to make independent decisions, and a sense of legal responsibility.

Such an educational system should not be limited to school law classes, but should be implemented through psychological trainings, case studies based on real-life events, legal forums, educational models of court proceedings, "Young lawyers' clubs," interactive legal quizzes, and media education on social networks. Also, in cooperation with the Supreme Court, the prosecutor's office, internal affairs bodies, the bar, and the mahalla system, legal education will form an integrated model of prevention with social institutions.

For the effectiveness of legal education, the use of innovative pedagogical methods - projective education, interactive education, an emotional-intellectual approach (EQ-approach), and digital legal education platforms - is of great importance. Through this, minors acquire the skills of applying legal knowledge not only theoretically, but also in practice, analyzing life examples, and drawing correct conclusions.

Also, in order to improve the legal culture of students in Uzbekistan, increasing legal literacy through the "Legal Information Internet Portal," "Legal Bulletin," "Youth Notebook" platform, organizing online legal consulting services through law enforcement agencies' websites and social networks are recognized as modern forms of prevention.

Thus, legal education is not limited to providing knowledge, but is a strategic direction of prevention that ensures the formation of a person's legal culture, respect for the law, awareness of their rights and obligations, and their development as a lawful, responsible, and active citizen in society.

In the USA, the program of legal education for minors is aimed at forming the legal consciousness and legal culture of young people, taking preventive measures against offenses, and ensuring socio-legal stability.

For example, the legal education program implemented in the state of Florida is intended for students in grades 7-8, and its main goal is to give young people an understanding of legal norms in society, the rights and duties of the individual, and the negative consequences of offenses. The measures applied within the framework of the Program include:

Measures aimed at mastering legal concepts are ensured by familiarizing minors with civil rights, the basics of criminal law, and legal norms;

Measures aimed at forming legal culture form the skills of making legal decisions in minors through interactive classes, role-playing games, and simulation court proceedings;

through social and moral educational measures, the negative social consequences of violations of the law, as well as the importance of observing the law for the individual and society, are explained.

in the process of legal education, teachers, psychologists, and employees of the local community contribute to the adaptation of young people to the social environment.

According to A.B. Guseynov, this program is an effective tool for the development of legal awareness and legal culture among young people, and its implementation will serve as an integral concept of preventive measures aimed at reducing future cases of juvenile delinquency[6].

Also, in the USA, legal education programs are supported not only in schools, but also through local communities and non-governmental organizations. This allows young people to apply legal knowledge in various social environments, ensuring their social and psychological stability[7].

Based on the experience of the USA, the following mechanisms can be effective in the formation of legal education programs for minors in Uzbekistan:

creation of centers of legal education in educational institutions and mahallas;

conducting interactive classes in cooperation with legal and psychological specialists;

creation of an integrated prevention system with society and the family;

development of programs providing for rehabilitation and social reintegration

References:

1. Effectiveness of Restorative Justice Principles in Juvenile Justice: A Meta Analysis - Wilson, D.B.; Olagere, A.; Kimbrell, C. S. (2017). P. 145.; Adilov B.Q. The Concept of Juvenile Delinquency and Measures for its Prevention. Volume 3 No 10 (2023): Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/21402/14313>; Shonazarov U. Theoretical analysis of the concept of juvenile delinquency. 2021. file:///C:/Users/User/Downloads/Yurisprudensiya 2021_39.pdf
2. Adilov B.Q. The Concept of Juvenile Delinquency and Measures for its Prevention. Volume 3 No 10 (2023): Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/21402/14313>
3. Wilson, H., et al. Restorative Justice for Juvenile Offenders: Legal Frameworks and Implementation. London: Routledge, 2017. - P. 78-85.
4. Tashtemirov, K., Kurchiboyev, J. Institutional cooperation and legislative foundations in juvenile prevention. - Tashkent: Institute Publishing House, 2024. - B. 33-40.
5. Babahanov, A., & Davlatov, S. Juvenile Delinquency Prevention: International and National Practices. - Tashkent: Science Press, 2025. - P. 102-110.

6.Guseynov A.B. Preventive measures in the development of legal awareness and legal culture of minors. Tashkent: 2019, pp. 45-52.

7.Snyder, H. N., & Sickmund, M. Juvenile Offenders and Victims: 2018 National Report. Washington, DC: Office of Juvenile Justice and Delinquency Prevention. Field, B. C. Children, Cops, and Confessions: Inside the Juvenile Justice System. New York: NYU Press. pp. 78-95

